
STUDY ON CURING KINETICS AND CURING PROCESS OF CF/BPR COMPOSITE

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ABSTRACT

In this work, curing kinetics of boron modified phenolic resin (BPR) was investigated and lightweight carbon fiber reinforced boron modified phenolic resin (CF/BPR) was prepared by the double-stage isothermal heating curing. Further, the effect of the heating rate during curing process on the compressive strength of CF/BPR was investigated. The curing of BPR needed more energy and the curing temperature of BPR under different condition was higher than that of virgin phenolic resin (PR). The heating rate during the curing process had the effect on the compressive strength of CF/BPR. With increasing heating rate during the curing process, the micro-cracks increased and the compressive strength of CF/BPR decreased. Once the heating rate exceeded a certain value, the micro-cracks no longer increased and the heating rate had little effect on the compressive strength. The heating rate should be considered during the curing process of CF/BPR.

1. Introduction

Thermal Protection System (TPS) for space capsules that execute atmospheric entries at hypersonic velocities [1, 2] (in excess of $11 \text{ km}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$ during reentry) are based on ablative materials. Lightweight carbon fiber reinforced phenolic resin (CF/PR) as a new lightweight thermal protection material, with phenolic resin as matrix and carbon fiber as reinforced material, is of particular interest to researchers [3~5]. Phenolic resin (PR) is the most important candidate matrix for ablative composites due to its low cost, excellent ablative properties and chemical resistance. But phenolic resin can induce a certain amount of shrinkage and generates water as a byproduct during the curing reaction [6], which limits the performance of phenolic resin and phenolic resin-based composite.

Some researchers have been investigated the curing process of phenolic resin and phenolic resin-based composites [7~10]. Curing kinetics based on thermal analysis techniques is most commonly and widely used to predict curing temperature and curing time. At present, DSC technique has been widely used to follow the curing reactions. Unfortunately, the heating rate during the conventional heating curing process is seldom considered.

In this work, curing kinetics of boron modified phenolic resin (BPR) was investigated by means

of non-isothermal Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) method based on Kissinger method and Ozawa method respectively. The curing process of CF/BPR, especially the effect of the heating rate during the curing process on the compressive strength of CF/BPR was investigated.

2. Experimental procedures

2.1 Materials

The purity of absolute ethanol (Sinopharm Chemical Reagent Co.,Ltd, China) was $\geq 99.7\%$ and the PR used was BPR (THC-400, Shaanxi Taihang Impedefire Polymer Co.,Ltd., China). THC-400 can be soluble in ethanol and insoluble in water. Carbon fiber needled preform (Tianniaohigh and new technology Co.,Ltd., Jiangsu, China) was made with carbon fiber weftless tape and carbon fiber felt by the means of needling and the density was $0.32 \text{ g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$ as shown in Fig.1. All of carbon fiber were polyacrylonitrile (PAN) based carbon fiber (T700SC-12000-50C, Toray, Japan). Further, fibers used in this work did not undergo any additional surface treatments like coating the carbon fibers or a thermal treatment of the carbon fibers prior to their impregnation with the phenolic resin.

2.2 Preparation of CF/BPR

CF/BPR was prepared in sequence by the vacuum-impregnation, drying and curing processes. Carbon fiber needled preform was placed in the vacuum oven and impregnated with 25% phenolic ethanol solution at room temperature. The curing of CF/BPR adopted the double-stage isothermal heating curing method, and the curing process was determined by the results of DSC test and compressive strength test.

2.3 Characterization

Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) tests were carried out with Q-20 (TA instruments, USA) in the nitrogen atmosphere at different heating rates of $5 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$, $10 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$, $15 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$, $20 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$.

According to the standards GB/T 1448-2005 [11], CF/BPR samples of $13\text{mm}\times 13\text{mm}\times 25\text{mm}$ were cut off from prepared CF/BPR and were subjected to compressive test using compressive tester (WDW-100D, Jinan Shijin Co., Ltd, Shandong, China) at a strain rate of $2 \text{ mm}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$.

The scanning electron microscope (SEM, S-4800, Hitachi, Japan) was used to observe the morphology of CF/BPR. The surfaces of CF/BPR samples were gold coated prior to analysis.

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Curing characteristic temperatures of BPR

The curing characteristic temperature, including the starting curing temperature (T_s), the peak curing temperature (T_p) and the finished curing temperature (T_f), can be used to describe the curing process of thermosetting resin and can be obtained by the means of the DSC test. The curing

characteristic temperatures at different heating rates (β) of 5 °C·min⁻¹, 10 °C·min⁻¹, 15 °C·min⁻¹, 20 °C·min⁻¹ are shown in Table 1.

$\beta/(\text{°C}\cdot\text{min}^{-1})$	$T_s/\text{°C}$	$T_p/\text{°C}$	$T_f/\text{°C}$
5	124	140	183
10	129	150	190
15	133	157	195
20	137	162	203

Table 1 Curing characteristic temperatures at the different heating rates

3.2 Curing kinetics of BPR

Kissinger method and Ozawa method were used to calculate the apparent activation energy of curing reaction of BPR. Kissinger and Ozawa equations are respectively shown in Eq.1 and Eq.2.

$$\ln\left(\frac{\beta}{T_p^2}\right) = \ln\left(\frac{AR}{E}\right) - \frac{E}{RT_p} \quad (1)$$

$$\lg \beta = \lg\left(\frac{AE}{RG(\alpha)}\right) - 2.315 - 0.4567E / RT \quad (2)$$

where E is the apparent activation energy, R is gas constant, α is the degree of reaction and $G(\alpha)$ is the curing reaction mechanism function of integration. Using Eq.1 and Eq.2, the apparent activation energy E can be calculated by the slope of the linear fitting curves of $\ln(\beta/T_p^2)$ vs. $1/T_p * 1000$ and $\lg \beta$ vs. $1/T_p * 1000$.

The reaction order n of curing reaction of BPR can be calculated, according to Crane equation (shown in Eq.3) and E.

$$\frac{d(\ln \beta)}{d(1/T_p)} = -E / nR \quad (3)$$

As seen in Eq.3, the reaction order n can be calculated by the slope of the linear fitting curve of $\ln \beta$ vs. $1/T_p * 1000$. The obtained curing kinetics parameters (including the apparent activation energy E and the reaction order n) of BPR are shown in Table 2.

	$E/(\text{kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1})$	n
Kissinger	87.028	0.946
Ozawa	89.462	0.972

Table 2 Curing kinetics parameters of BPR

Although the results obtained by Kissinger method were slightly less than the results obtained by Ozawa method, the results obtained by the two methods were very close. This indicated that the

obtained results are reliable. E of curing reaction of BPR obtained by Kissinger method and Ozawa method were $87.028 \text{ kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$ and $89.462 \text{ kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$ respectively which are more than that of virgin PR (approximately $73 \text{ kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$). It indicates that the curing of BPR needs more energy and the curing temperatures of BPR are higher than that of virgin PR. This trend can be supported by the results reported by Wang et al. [12]. The reaction orders of curing reaction of BPR obtained by Kissinger method and Ozawa method were 0.946 and 0.972 respectively.

3.3 Determination of curing temperature of CF/BPR

The curing reaction of thermosetting resin includes three parameters: the curing temperature, the curing time and the heating rate. Generally, the determination of curing temperature can adopt the T- β extrapolation method. Namely the linear relationship exists between temperature T and heating rate β . The plot of T vs. β is drawn, the straight line is fitted by linear fitting and then the curing characteristic temperature at the isothermal heating curing process can be obtained when extrapolation reaches $\beta = 0$. The plots of T vs. β is shown in Fig.1.

Fig.1 Plots of T vs. β

When $\beta = 0$, namely the isothermal heating curing adopted, T_s , T_p , T_f were respectively $120 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, $134 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and $176.5 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. In this work, the curing of CF/BPR adopted the double-stage isothermal heating curing method. Hence, the curing temperatures of two stages can be chose at $130 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and $170 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ respectively. The curing time of two stages can choose one hour (1h) and three hours (3h), according to the data provided by the manufacturer.

3.4 Effect of the heating rate on the compressive strength of CF/BPR

The curing of CF/BPR adopted the double-stage isothermal heating curing method and the curing

temperature and the curing time were also determined. The curing process of CF/BPR is shown in Fig.2. The heating rate during the curing process is the rate of temperatures rising between room temperature and 130 °C and between 130 °C and 170 °C.

Fig.2 Curing process of CF/BPR

According to the curing process shown in Fig.3, CF/BPR samples were prepared at the heating rate of 1 °C·min⁻¹, 3 °C·min⁻¹, 5 °C·min⁻¹, 7 °C·min⁻¹ respectively and the compressive strength of CF/BPR prepared at each heating rate was obtained by the average of five specimens in the compressive strength test. The effect of the heating rate on compressive strength of CF/BPR is shown in Fig.3. The heating rate has an obvious effect on the compressive strength and the compressive strength of CF/BPR prepared at the heating rate of 1 °C·min⁻¹ was higher about 17% than that of CF/BPR prepared at the heating rate of 7 °C·min⁻¹.

Fig.3 Effect of heating rate on compressive strength of CF/BPR

The SEM images of CF/BPR prepared at the heating rate of 1~7 $^{\circ}\text{C}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ are shown in Fig.5. When the heating rate is 1 $^{\circ}\text{C}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$, the micro-cracks barely existed. When the heating rate increased to 3 $^{\circ}\text{C}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$, the micro-cracks increased. But the few micro-cracks existed in the joint between resin and fiber. When the heating rate increased to 5 $^{\circ}\text{C}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$, the micro-cracks continued to increase and there existed lots of micro-cracks in the joint between resin and fiber. When the heating rate increased from 5 $^{\circ}\text{C}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ to 7 $^{\circ}\text{C}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$, the micro-cracks no longer increased. With heating rate increasing, the temperature difference between interior and exterior of material increases and the heat stress increases, so that more micro-cracks can be generated. When heating rate increases to a certain value (5 $^{\circ}\text{C}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$), the micro-cracks no longer increase and the effect of the heating rate on the compressive strength becomes very little. These results were consistent with the results of the compressive tests.

Fig.5 SEM images of CF/BPR prepared at the heating rate of 1~7 °C·min⁻¹: (a) 1 °C·min⁻¹, (b) high-magnification of (a), (c) 3 °C·min⁻¹, (d) high-magnification of (c), (e) 5 °C·min⁻¹, (f) high-magnification of (e), (g) 7 °C·min⁻¹, (h) high-magnification of (g).

4. Conclusion

CF/BPR was successfully prepared by the double-stage isothermal heating curing method. The curing kinetics of boron modified phenolic resin and the effect of the heating rate during the curing process on the compressive strength of CF/BPR were investigated in detail. The curing reaction of BPR is complicated. The curing of BPR needs more energy and the curing temperatures of BPR are higher

than that of virgin PR. The heating rate during the curing process had an obvious effect on the compressive strength and the compressive strength of CF/BPR prepared at the heating rate of $1\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ was higher about 17% than that of CF/BPR prepared at the heating rate of $7\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$. With the heating rate during the curing process increasing, the compressive strength of CF/BPR decreases, due to the micro-cracks increasing. However, when the heating rate during the curing process increased to a certain value, the micro-cracks no longer increase and the effect of the heating rate on the compressive strength becomes insignificant. The heating rate should be considered during the curing process of CF/BPR.

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